

Research Article

Industrial Attachment Report On Royal Pharmaceuticals Company

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ABSTRACT

This In-Plant Training is performed as a fulfillment of the MBA-FM program. It's an honor to be a member of Royal Pharmaceuticals Pvt. Ltd. During my implant training at Royal, I was posted to different departments namely Production (PR), Quality Control (QC), Quality Assurance (QA), Warehouse (WH), Engineering and Maintenance and finance department. Undoubtedly, I have gained an immense practical knowledge on manufacturing of different drugs, quality control of raw materials, bulk products, semi-finished products, finished products, quality assurance, storage and handling of raw material and packaging material, engineering and maintenance along with finance and administration department. Moreover, I have also been aware of importance of documentation for the continuation of safety manufacturing of different medicines. The In-Plant training, as per syllabus of TU to fulfill completion of MBA-FM degree program of Balkumari College affiliated to Tribhuvan University (TU) was undertaken at Royal Pharmaceuticals Pvt. Ltd. We had a training of 3 months and those days were very fruitful and were proved to be very much admirable in our managerial activities. This in-plant training gave us a clear picture about what industrial scenario is all about and how each department are interlinked as well as what activities are to performed there on day to day basis in context to production and quality of pharmaceutical products.

INTRODUCTION

The students of Master in Business Administration of Tribhuvan University have been assigned to perform 13 weeks internship on a particular institution and to make an internship report accordingly. This task has been assigned by Management Faculty of the Tribhuvan University as a partial fulfillment of requirement for the Degree of MBA program.

The internship program is a practical of all the subjects learned in the classrooms and it comprises of the three crucial credit hours. It is the process of working as an assistant to gain practical experience and skills in an occupation. The main objective of the internship is to help students understand the real working environment as well as to apply the knowledge they have gained in the classroom into the real business practices. It gives

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an opportunity to observe, learn, and understand the corporate culture, acquire knowledge and skills in the respective field which helps the students in their further career development.

In MBA course, every student should go through the eight weeks long internship in any industry relating to their specialized subject and it provides practical exposure and helps the students to understand corporate social responsibility, develop corporate attitude and venture entrepreneurship. As a student of MBA, I got an opportunity to do my internship in Royal Pharmaceuticals Pvt. Ltd.

During the period, I observed how the department functions. This is a great opportunity for me to know about the management and accounting in the pharmaceutical field. I find out the importance of communication, management skill, and technological information management in the pharmaceutical industry as well as marketing department of the industry that has worked as a building block for career development in this financial service sector department.

Though Royal is Pharmaceutical industry there is application of management skill information and technology in its business activities at different levels. Its financial activities are monitored by the financial analyst.

Objectives of the study

General Objectives: To know the overall functioning, managing and organization of pharmaceutical industry.

Specific Objectives

- a) To be familiar with the organization structure, departments and their roles in the functioning of the industry.
- b) To get basic framework about the implementation of the WHO-GMP principle in the industry.
- c) To get knowledge about the machineries, their engineering and the working principle.

- d) To gain the practical knowledge about the production, quality analysis and documentation.
- e) To be familiarized with the different analytical instruments used in the analysis.
- f) To be aware of various formulation aspects & their manufacturing process.
- g) To build up the self confidence to work as the industrial pharmacist.
- h) To understand inventory management of raw and finished products and the process of product recall.
- i) To know the importance of the financial analyst in the pharmaceutical company.
- j) To find the importance of the management at different level of activities carries out at pharmaceuticals industry.

To determine the growth and development of pharmaceuticals company on the basis of economic point view.

Methodology

Research methodology simply refers to the practical “how” of any given piece of research. More specifically, it’s about how a researcher systematically designs a study to ensure valid and reliable results that address the research aims and objectives. There are various research methodologies that can be used to do a research. The research can be quantitative and qualitative. Qualitative research refers to research which focuses on collecting and analyzing words (written or spoken) and textual data, whereas quantitative research focuses on measurement and testing using numerical data. Qualitative analysis can also focus on other “softer” data points, such as body language or visual elements. Here both the methods have been used.

Data were collected from the primary and secondary source. Primary source includes self search and investigation. Secondary source includes annual reports and brochures, magazines and published documents. Most of the data in this

report is gained from the experience from the works. During the preparation of the internship report, I took help of staff and group discussion with the friends. I also took data from web site.

Organization Selection

Every action is directed towards accomplishing certain objectives. Each kind of study has its own objectives. The general objective of this report is to partially fulfill the requirements for the degree of MBA and to understand the importance of MBA-FM in Pharmaceuticals industry, its structure, working procedures and risk associated with it. However, the specific objectives of the study are:

- a) To explore the applicability of theoretical knowledge in the practical workplace.
- b) To gather the knowledge on the various activities performed in various departments of the Pharmaceutical industry.
- c) To examine about the different products and services offered by Pharmaceutical industry.
- d) To develop the ability to handle various kinds of customers with varying knowledge level, problems and requirements.
- e) To monitor the exact use of finance and accounting to uplift profit/ income of Pharmaceutical industry.

Placement

As an officer, placed at different departments of Royal Pharmaceuticals Company.

Duration

I worked at Royal Pharmaceuticals Company as intern for 3 months.

Activities Performed in the Organization

MBA-FM aspirant goes through different subject matter during their course completion. With their only theoretical knowledge they won't be able to use their skill and knowledge in real market. So it's compulsory to involve in practical work using management skill and technology. Thus a report is important to be maintained as primary source of information for future use. Management and

communication is important to different department of Pharmaceuticals Company including marketing of the medicine in the market. The use of latest information technology has made the works easy to handle and so convenient to operate.

It aid in the identification of knowledge and skills essential to do well in a particular profession. Since student has real field exposure in professional life it gives overview for the student how the work life will be in coming days. It gives insights on owns strength and weakness. It also gives knowledge on what are the real market opportunities and threats. This helps student on what areas they should work on to compete in real world. This gives students the valuable experience in preparation for employment. The internship allows opportunities for the development of practical skills in context where professional criticism is immediate and constructive.

Successful completion of an internship often provides students with professional confidence. So internship is rudimentary in student's life. These are some significance of the internship. It also furnishes the student with the opportunities to observe and understand connections between coursework and skills needed for the effective work-life balance.

In the store department, I used to maintain the inventory records of raw materials, semi-finished, finished goods. FIFO, FEFO, LIFO were used.

In production department I used to calculate and monitor amount of the API, and Excipients require for the manufacturing of the dosage form of the medicine in the Royal Pharmaceuticals Company.

In QC Department, I used to handle the raw materials, semi-finished, finished goods and test their quality as per various guidelines and prepare the report accordingly.

In QA Department, I used to investigate the overall activities being takes place in Royal Pharmaceuticals Company.

In Finance Department, I used to look at the inflow and outflow of the income. Examine the income statements and balance sheet.

Limitation of the Study

In undertaking this study, a number of problems were faced. Thus the study has several limitations. The limitations are:

- a) Insufficient time to monitor all the financial activities. Improper guidance of the activities at Royal Pharmaceuticals Company.
- b) Lack of knowledge: As a student, in the research field, I have no past practical experience of data collection, data processing, data analyzing, integrating and presenting. So it is a limiting factor for obtain accurate information.
- c) Lack of time: For the time limitation I could not gather more information to justify exact condition. The time constraints are limiting factors.
- d) Small sample size: The study is limited by the size of the sample. As the sample size is very small, geographical and regional differences could not be included.
- e) Fund unavailability: I don't have much financial support to conduct this study. I could not interview with more respondents covering the survey area.
- f) Customer's willingness: Most of the customer of the company businessman and employee. So, they could not give me enough time to fill up questionnaire. Also they are not willing or afraid to provide appropriate data.

Introduction of the Industry

Royal Pharmaceuticals was established in the year 2017 at Bharatpur-16, Chitwan, Nepal. It was a pioneering venture in the area of pharmaceuticals products, aimed addressing a big vacuum in the market for high quality products. Our offered products are manufactured using optimum quality raw materials, in tandem with international quality standards by a team of highly qualified and

experienced professionals. Further we make sure these products are available to the customers at affordable prices in the market, within stipulated time frame, in order to stand efficiently by their expectations.

We have wide range of Cardio Vascular drugs, Diabetic drugs and General drugs in forms of Tablets, Capsules (Hard and Soft Gel) and Semisolids of top quality standards as per WHO-GMP guidelines with attractive packing. We are WHO-GMP and National GMP certified company. We supply our products to most of the hospitals, healthcare centers for competitive price. It is our endeavor to provide quality healthcare products at extremely affordable prices to our customers.

Presently we have 38 General products and 34 Cardiac and Diabetic products which are marketed.

Origin/ History/ Development of the Industry

The site is located in Sharanpur, Bharatpur-16 in Chitwan District. It is about 12 Km south from Sahid chowk, Bharatpur-3, Chitwan by pitch road from the main highway that links Narayangarh, which is an industrial and commercial town of Nepal. The site being located in a village far from the city is free from various urban pollutions.

The site is building in **18 kattha 6.75 Dhur** lands and consists of single building structures -a three storey building with production, RM & Primary PM stores, secondary change rooms, secondary packing and finished goods store, & Administration (Security Guard) in the ground floor while the first floor comprises the Mezzanine (service floor), control under Engineering and Maintenance Department and Quality Assurance, R & D, Quality Control and Microbiology Department. Second Floor consists of further expansion civil construction has been completed (for Cepha and Sterile Section 14000 sq. ft) and RO Plant (as utility area).

A separate powerhouse for the Generator is located towards the south east. The building is a three-storey building with about 10,000 sq. ft. on the ground floor, about 10,000 sq. ft. on the first floor and 10,000 sq. ft. on the second floor. The whole Building was constructed in the year 2017-2019. No other manufacturing activities are carried out at the site except for the pharmaceutical manufacturing.

This project proposes the establishment of new modern modular facilities pharmaceutical formulation plant (RPPL) with annual capacity of 150.00 million pcs. of Tablets, 45.00 million pcs. of Hard Gelatin Capsule & 20.00 million pcs. of Soft Gelatin Capsule and 20.00 million pcs. of Topical Preparations (Ointments and Creams etc) at full capacity utilization of one shift 8 hr. manufacturing.

Our History:

2017 to 2019- Plant Construction and R&D started
2019- Product Manufactured and Lunched to Market

2022- WHO-GMP and National GMP certificate received.

Mission:

- a) To improve the quality of life, productivity and dignity of the people through outstanding healthcare solutions.
- b) To develop reliable strategic partnerships and maintain a sustainable marketing system that ensures access to affordable and high quality products.
- c) To retain and nurture a highly industrious, self motivated and dedicated team.

Vision:

The preferred provider of affordable, sustainable and innovative healthcare solutions for a healthy human.

Classification of the Industry

Royal Pharmaceuticals Pvt. Ltd. comprises of young, energetic and dedicated professionals who

have the expertise knowledge and perception to innovate and fulfill the needs of the market.

Royal Pharmaceuticals Pvt. Ltd. is constantly exercising critical thinking to maintain professional competence for excelling the quality of its products.

Royal Pharmaceuticals Pvt. Ltd. will always embrace highest standard of character to serve and promote quality of life through quality product with higher performance.

Royal Pharmaceuticals Pvt. Ltd. is endowed with distinct departments of R&D, QC, QA & Production to ensure the quality drugs. The infrastructure of factory is completely equipped with all the requirements of all guidelines without any compromise, which is backed by the most advanced technology and competent technical personnel.

functions of the Industry

Management: The overall management of the organization is headed by the Chairman, Managing Director and Technical & Factory Operation Director, having experience of successfully managing the enterprise for more than two decades. The promoters as well as the Departmental Managers of the company comprises various professional people with good technical, educational and professional background in enterprise management.

Future Plan: Royal Pharmaceuticals is constantly on the move to improve, to grow and to serve better. It plans to launch many useful and innovative biopharmaceuticals, cosmeceuticals, nutraceuticals, sterile, Cephalosporin and veterinary products in the days ahead.

Formulation and Research Development: The plant has a separate Formulation Development Suite adjoining Q C Laboratory with separate AHU to maintain Class 100,000 Area. Complete set of most modern wall mounted Granulating, Blending, Compression & Coating Machines are housed in this suite.

Production: Our state-of-the-art manufacturing plant is located at Sharanpur, Bharatpur-16, Chitwan, Nepal. Currently, we have a facility of producing highest quality Tablets, Soft-gelatin capsules, Hard gelatin capsules, Topical-Preparation (Ointment, Cream, Lotion, Gel, Shampoo etc.) and Powder to meet the demanding market of the present day. The production processes have been adopted and validated not only to meet with all guidelines but also to meet the requirement of other international regulatory agencies.

Quality Assurance: Royal Pharmaceuticals accords highest emphasis on the quality of the products and services. Its Quality Assurance Department is fully self-reliant having support from Quality Control Department with sophisticated instruments along with highly qualified and trained personnel to ensure the Quality Assurance of the products in conformity with the quality standards of International Compendia.

Quality Control: Royal department is equipped with many of the advance instruments like HPLC (High performance liquid chromatography), FT-IR (Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy), Automatic Potentiometric and Karl fisher Titration Apparatus etc. All these instruments are being utilized for testing of raw materials, packing materials and finished products at different stages as per the needs. It also operates a full-fledged microbiological testing facility, which is in line with international standards.

Engineering & Maintenance (HVAC System): The plant has the latest and modern HVAC system with altogether 25 numbers of AHU's designed for tablet, Topical Preparation and capsule section only.

All AHUs have been imported from Carrier make India with German and Korean technology which is only one of its kind's in the country. Purified

water generation system with recent technology i.e. EDI system with UV light.

Also have ETP system, Compressor, Generator and Separate Work shop for necessary and smooth function of plant.

Sales & Distribution: We have a good and wide network all over Nepal for sales and distribution of our products.

Business Development Team: Our Marketing team is well experienced, motivated and hard working for promotion of our products throughout Nepal.

Ownership/BOD/Management Team

Name of company	Royal Pharmaceuticals Pvt. Ltd.
Address of Head Office Telephone / Fax No:	Belchowk, Bharatpur-03, Chitwan, Nepal +977-56-571005
Contact Person (I): Designation: E-Mail	Mr. Prem Thapa Chairman royalpharmainfo@gmail.com
Contact Person (II): Designation:	Mr. Keshav Lamichamae Managing Director
Address of Factory Telephone No:	Sharanpur, Bharatpur-16, Chitwan, Nepal -----
Contact Person (I) Designation E-Mail:	Mr. Pawan Kumar Sah Director, Technical & Operation (Factory) royalpharmainfo@gmail.com
Address of Marketing Office Telephone / Fax No:	House No. 83, SachetanMarg, SangamChowk, New Baneshwor, Kathmandu, Nepal +977 1 4109272
Contact Person (I): Designation: E-Mail	Mr. Uddhav Babu Tripathi Marketing, HOD royalpharmamkt@gmail.com

ANALYSIS OF OBJECTIVES DONE/ PROBLEMS SOLVED

Department/ Unit/ Section

The following departments were contributing towards the goal achievements: production department, quality assurance, quality control, Engineering and maintenance, sale and distribution, business development, account department, finance department etc.

SWOT Analysis of Department/Unit/Section

A strategic plan or mission for the future begins with an assessment of the current situation in which the organization exists. The organization has to analyze the potential strengths to gain competitive advantage. It helps to predict the possible opportunities to capture the possible gains and advantages for growth and development. SWOT comprises of strengths and weaknesses which are the internal factors and opportunities and threats which are the external factors that affect the organization.

Strengths:

- a) Use of latest technology.
- b) Well, classified products and services catering the needs of customers and provides customer friendly environment.
- c) Qualified personnel, highly qualified and skilled personnel.
- d) Strong application GMP Guidelines and thus quality drugs are produced.
- e) Strong marketing head with strong communication skill of the marketing team.
- f) Proper financial management and proper forecasting of sales and demands of the product.
- g) Strong coordination and well managed supply chain system.

Weaknesses:

- a) There is lack of sufficient staff (understaffed). Too much responsibilities lies on single person.
- b) Most of the customers are of old age which creates problem in dealing with them.
- c) Space occupied is congested which creates inconvenience to their customers.

- d) Lack of marketing resources.
- e) Improper guidance and lack of sense of responsibility.
- f) There is improper time schedule for consumption sales and distribution of the products.
- g) Lack of motivation and awareness program among the personnel.
- h) Lack of proper involvement and consideration of the thought of the individual in the decision making.
- i) Lack of bonus, increment, personal growth, training time to time.

Opportunities:

- a) Investment in the various projects like nutraceuticals, tourism, hydropower etc.
- b) Increasing level of awareness among the customers regarding the service provided.
- c) Increasing brand and branches, domestic and international market.
- d) Increasing in large number of product and services, products and high involvement of company in business, education, industry, agriculture etc.
- e) Increasing awareness program regarding social and mental health.
- f) Increasing the involvement of individual in the decision making.

Threats:

- a) The market is overcrowded with financial company/ institutions and high competition.
- b) Improper balance between demand and supply.
- c) Lack of security regarding natural disaster and accident.
- d) Lack of proper management of consequence of strike, domestic violence.
- e) Market instability due to political instability, economic slowdown.
- f) The market is highly competitive with large no. of pharmaceuticals industry.

- g) False marketing regarding quality of product and services.
 - h) The threat of substitute as the services provided by most of the banks is moreover same and nowadays other organization also provides substitute services.
 - i) NRB regulation is changing day by day and various restrictions have been amended frequently.
 - j) Unhealthy competition and lack of proper education and awareness among the people.
- g) Verify that documents related to every batch of product are complete.
 - h) Ensure that Batch Processing records are properly filed and kept for the required period of time and that they are accessible to authorized persons.
 - i) Ensure that there is a recall procedure and take self initiative for activating recalls if necessary.
 - j) All necessary controls on intermediate products and any other in-process controls and validations are carried out.
 - k) Satisfactory arrangement exists to ensure, as far as possible that the products are stored, distributed and subsequently handled so that quality is maintained throughout their shelf life.
 - l) Vendor audits & Approvals
 - m) Continuous training of personnel is carried out & adapted according to need.
 - n) Quality Management System covers the following system.

Problem Solved

Quality Management System:

The quality committee contributes to the implementation of the quality management system to achieve the defined objectives.

To communicate to the staff's about the quality policy and quality objectives, to make the staff familiar with the processes used to achieve compliance with quality requirements. This should facilitate the implementation of the quality management system as well as ensure its maintenance and required updates during altering circumstances. This should also allow effective communication and control of quality related activities and a documented base for quality system audits.

Description of the QMS:

- a) The company will an up-to-standards and up-to-date cGMP quality system.
- b) Products are manufactured, tested and released as per Current Good manufacturing.
- c) Practices and Good Laboratory Practices into the premises (i.e. QC Lab).
- d) Check that approved Standard Operating Procedures is followed.
- e) Plan and carry out Self-inspections and follow up.
- f) Ensure that all documents like specification and protocol are kept upto date, properly used, signed, followed and filed.

Product Recall:

Recall: Refers to the withdrawal of a specific batch (es) of the drug product from the market.

A batch shall be recalled from the market, when it is found by the Head – Quality Assurance, that the batch does not meet regulatory requirement/specification. The parameters which would need the recall of any product would include but not limited to:

- a) Product mix-ups and label mix-ups.
- b) Physical and visual deterioration like significant discoloration.
- c) Failure to meet Regulatory Specification (such as Assay etc.,)
- d) Recall notice from the regulatory authority
- e) Failure of the Control/Stability sample.

Change Control

Change control: Change control is a quality tool and a management to maintain and keep the records of all changes as a history. Changes can be

related to facility, documentation, system, equipment, instrument, procedure, layouts and products etc.

Category of changes

Changes can be categorized into three types:-

1. Minor
2. Major
3. Critical

Quality Circle and Management Review

It is defined as a way of capturing the creative and innovative power that lies within the work force.

A quality circle is a small group of volunteers doing similar work i.e. Quality Policy maintain and quality application work into premises.

Quality Circle and meeting carried every three month, under the leadership of their immediate supervisor to-

- a) Identify problems
- b) Set priorities
- c) Discover cause
- d) Propose solution

The problem may concern-

- a) Quality
- b) Productivity
- c) Safety
- d) Job Structure
- e) Process flow

Thus Quality circle is a participative management system in which suggestions and improvements for the betterment of organization.

Corrective and Preventive Action

Corrective Action:

A corrective action is a reaction to a problem that has already occurred. It assumes that a nonconformance or problem exists and has been reported by either internal or external sources.

Preventive Action:

A preventive action is initiated to stop a potential problem from occurring. It assumes that adequate monitoring and controls are in place in the quality system to assure that potential problems are identified and eliminated before they happen.

If something in the quality system indicates that a possible problem is or may develop, a preventive action must be implemented to avert and then eliminate the potential situation. The documentation for a preventive action provides evidence that an effective quality system has been implemented that is able to anticipate, identify and eliminate potential problems.

A timely, well documented, Corrective / Preventive Action program validates a quality system that is not only capable of identifying potential problems but also effectively correcting them when they do occur.

Overview of Root Cause Analysis

A root cause analysis is a means to get to the bottom of a problem or unexpected event. Root-cause analyses aim at improving products or processes – quality – and they must be undertaken in systematic ways in order to be effective. The general processes for undertaking a root cause analysis are:

- a) Describe the problem your company is looking at
- b) Gather data associated with the problem
- c) Identify potential causes for the problem
- d) Identify which causes you will remove or change in order to prevent repeat problems
- e) Identify solutions that will be effective in preventing repeat problems
- f) Implement changes
- g) Observe changes to ensure that they have effectively eliminated the problem

CONCLUSION AND LESSON LEARNT

Conclusion

After the internship at Royal Pharmaceuticals Company I found real experience of using my knowledge and information. I found at Royal Pharmaceuticals Company is a leading cGMP certified company which has been serving the mankind by supplying general and cardiac medicine. There is equaled important of every subject of science and technology. Management

and accounting activities are being operated carefully and important to uplift the economic status of the organization. The knowledge regarding, management of inventory, sales and distribution helped in the marketing as well.

Financial activities helped the finance analyst to monitor the income statement, balance sheet and various others statement which can monitor the inflow and outflow of the cash. Management information system and communication skill help to improve the profit of the organization.

Lesson Learnt

- a) Use of financial knowledge and management information system help a lot to manage administrative works and below activities in a proper systemic way.
- b) Due to knowledge of the finance we can easily monitor the growth and development of the organization.
- c) With the knowledge of the finance and accounting we can choose the type of investment for the future business growth.
- d) After the study we are able to analyze the risk factors and promoting factors of the business.
- e) We can be able to know turn over the ratio, profit ratio, ABITA, Equity, capital and liabilities, debt and equity ratio of the organization.
- f) From the knowledge of finance we can choose suitable and profitable type of shareholders for our business.

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